

Performance of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites under Different Environments

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ABSTRACT

Composite properties being of two types, matrix controlled and fibre controlled, will be affected differently under different environmental conditions. An experimental study has been performed to study the effect of sea water and normal boiling water on the performance of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites and carbon/kevlar hybrid composites. Percentage moisture absorbed decreases with increase in thickness of the composites and is much higher for bi-directional composites than for unidirectional composites. Flexural strength as well as interlaminar shear strength of the composites deteriorate after immersion in water. This effect is more predominant in sea water particularly for bi-directional hybrid composites.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites have been developed intensively over the past two decades. Because of their applications in aerospace industry, rigorous tests have been made to evaluate performance of these composites under actual service conditions, which besides other factors included environmental conditions as well (1,2). Under basic environmental conditions, these materials are likely to experience the effect of water, high humidity and thermal cycling. Extensive studies have been made (3-5) to study the effect of moisture and temperature on the properties of carbon fibre reinforced composites. It has been generally accepted that though carbon fibres are chemically inert, their composites absorb moisture and result in degradation of mechanical properties at elevated temperatures (3,4), the amount of loss being dependent on the composite formulation. All these studies have been made with respect to some particular resin system.

Besides aerospace applications, carbon fibre reinforced composites are being used in marine applications as well (6), wherein it is subjected to humid conditions of sea water. Present studies

have been made to study the effect of sea water on carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites and carbon/kevlar hybrid composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Present studies have been made with Torayaca T-300B, 6000-50B carbon fibre, Torayaca carbon fibre cloth type 6141 and kevlar 49 cloth style 281. Commercial epoxy resin system (LY 556 + HT 972) produced by M/s.CIBA GEIGY of India was used.

Composites Preparation

Carbon fibre prepregs were made by wet winding technique. These prepregs were pressed under heated rollers so as to have desired amount of resin content.

Unidirection carbon fibre reinforced composites were made by putting the cut prepregs in a mould Die (20cm x 15cm). Mould Die was placed between the heated plates of a press and curing of the composites was carried out as per prescribed curing cycle. Composites of different thicknesses were made by varying the number of plies. Bi-directional composites were made with Torayaca carbon fibre cloth style 6141 and similar prepregging technique. Hybrid composites were made with Torayaca carbon fibre cloth style 6141 and kevlar 49 cloth style 281. Composites were made with different arrangements of Carbon/Kevlar lay up.

Specimens of size 20cm x 1cm were cut from the above composites. Some of these specimens were tested for flexural strength, shear strength and impact strength at room temperature while some were conditioned in water as described in section below and tested.

Experiments Under Water

Specimens cut in size were preconditioned in an oven at temperature 60-70°C to remove any absorbed moisture and cooled in a desiccator. These specimens were then put in sea water kept at 23°C. The specimens were taken out periodically and weighed to calculate moisture absorbed. Precautions were taken to remove water film at the surface of the composites i.e. the composites were surface dried to find out amount of water actually absorbed. Flexural strength and Interlaminar shear strength of these composites were measured. Some of these composites were dried in oven to remove absorbed moisture completely. Mechanical properties of these composites were also measured.

Some of the specimens were put in the boiling water for different times and their moisture up take was calculated. These were also tested for mechanical properties.

Testing

Wet as well as dry composites were tested for mechanical properties with Instron Universal testing machine 1122. Flexural strength of the composites was measured by three point bending technique using span to thickness ratio of 32:1. Shear strength of the composites was measured by three point loading using span to thickness ratio of 5:1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Absorption of Water by UD-Composites

Unidirection carbon fibre reinforced composites of different thicknesses but with same length, width and fibre volume content,

after properly drying were immersed in sea water. Increase in their weight was measured periodically to calculate the water absorbed by the composites. Figure 1 shows the water absorbed by these composites with time. It shows that moisture absorbed is very rapid in the beginning and it slows down appreciably after about twenty days. Thin composites attain a state of partial saturation after about fifty days whereas thick specimens continue to absorb moisture though at slow rate. At particular instant, percentage water absorbed by thick specimens is very much less than that for thin specimens (Fig.2). The effect is more pronounced in the thickness range 1mm to 5mm. That is why the upper layers of the composites absorb moisture quickly, while the innermost layers are still dry. Similar effect is noticed when these composites are immersed in boiling water. However, the total water absorbed after keeping the sample in boiling water for 100 hours is more than total sea water absorbed (Fig.3). Heating up of the composites may facilitate quick and increased water absorption.

Absorption of water by Bi-directional composites

Figure 4 shows the sea water absorbed by bi-directional carbon fibre and Carbon/Kevlar hybrid composites. These composites also show similar behaviour as unidirectional composites. However, the rate and extent of water absorption depending on the fibre type and lay up system. In case of composites with alternate single layers of carbon and kevlar fabrics, the water absorption is less than in those where two layers of kevlar fabrics are combined together in between two carbon fibre layers. Carbon/Kevlar hybrid composites with kevlar fabric at the top and bottom absorb more moisture than composites with equal fibre volume content but carbon fabric layers at the top and bottom. This may be attributed to the water absorption by kevlar fibre itself and through capillaries made between kevlar fibre and epoxy resin.

Mechanical Properties of UD Composites after water absorption

Figure 5 shows the flexural strength of UD Carbon Fibre composites after immersion in sea water for 80 days. Flexural strength of composites before immersion is shown in the upper solid curve (curve a). It is found that flexural strength of the composites falls down by 5-10% on absorption of sea water (curve c). Loss of flexural strength for thicker composites is less than for thinner composites. This is attributed to less water absorption by thicker composites.

Similar effects are noticed when composites are immersed in boiling water (curve b). But in this case the loss in flexural strength is less than that in case of immersion in sea water, though water absorbed in former case is higher. It shows that chemical compounds dissolved in sea water have also effect on the mechanical properties of the composites. These composites regain their flexural strength on removal of moisture (curve d), even in case of sea water.

Figure 6 shows the Inter-laminar shear strength of the composites after different water absorptions. Inter-laminar shear strength of the composites increase with increase in thickness up to 2.5mm and decreases with higher thickness (curve a). On immersion in sea water, composites show a noticeable decrease in shear strength (curve c). This effect is more pronounced for thicker specimens. Here also in case of treatment of the composites with boiling water, decrease in shear strength is observed (curve b) which is less than that observed on treatment with sea water. Decrease in shear strength on absorption of moisture is

because of formation of a cluster of water layer in the matrix system and weakening of the bonding between matrix and reinforcement. Here again the shear strength is regained on removal of moisture (curve d).

Mechanical properties of Bi-directional composites

Sea water absorption has been found to have pronounced effect on the mechanical properties of bi-directional composites, specially carbon/kevlar hybrid composites. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of these composites (dry as well as wet). It shows that all composites show fall in mechanical properties on sea water absorption. This fall is more for hybrid composites and specially composites with kevlar layer at top and bottom. This may be attributed to large water absorption by these composites which weakens the bonding between matrix and fibre. Surprisingly the mechanical properties are not regained on removal of absorbed water contrary to the phenomenon observed in uni-directional composites.

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TABLE 1
Mechanical Properties of bi-directional Composites before and
after water absorption

Sr.No.	Bi-Directional Composite System	Room Temperature Mechanical Properties		Properties after Sea Water absorption			Properties after removal of Sea Water	
		Flexural Strength MN/m ²	ILSS MN/m ²	Water Absorbed %	Flexural Strength MN/m ²	ILSS MN/m ²	Flexural Strength MN/m ²	ILSS MN/m ²
1	Carbon Fibre/Epoxy	1100	50	1.2	740	43	700	38
2	Carbon-Kevlar Epoxy	790	36	4.8	460	22.7	390	27.7
3	Kevlar-Carbon Epoxy	480	32	5.7	220	22	200	19

Fig. 1 SEA WATER ABSORBED WITH TIME BY UD CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES OF DIFFERENT THICKNESS.

Fig. 2 VARIATION OF MOISTURE ABSORBED WITH THICKNESS OF UD CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES IMMERSIED FOR 80 DAYS IN SEA WATER.

Fig.3. WATER ABSORBED (BOILING WATER) WITH THICKNESS OF U D CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES AFTER 100 HRS.

Fig.4. SEA WATER ABSORBED WITH TIME BY BIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER AND HYBRID COMPOSITES.

Fig. 5. EFFECT OF MOISTURE ABSORPTION ON THE FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF UD CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES OF DIFFERENT THICKNESS ($V_f = 40\%$)

Fig. 6. VARIATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF UD CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES.